

HIGHLY DRAPABLE ORGANIC SHEETS MADE OF RECYCLED CARBON STAPLE FIBER YARNS

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ABSTRACT

In order to sustainably establish carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPC) in the market on an industry scale, solutions on how to recycle these new materials have to be developed. Quasi-continuously aligned staple fiber structures in organic sheets made of recycled carbon fibers are one approach. The process chain as well as the mechanical properties will be presented. It will be shown that the processing of recycled carbon fibers (rCF) and polyamide 6 fibers into aligned rCF/PA6 staple fiber yarns (rCF-SFY) are a suitable solution for a true recycling of carbon fibers. In the conducted work rCF spooling cut-offs were spun into rCF-SFY and subsequently processed into non-crimp fabrics (NCF). These NCF were pressed into unidirectional (UD) laminates as well as in organic sheets. Achievable tensile strengths for rCF-SFY UD laminates are 1255 MPa, tensile moduli are 94 GPa, which represents a 80% level of virgin CFRPC (vCFRPC). Moreover, the specific feature of rCF-SFY to be able to plastically deform under process temperature of the used PA6 matrix (staple fiber effect), enabling new degrees of deep-drawing of CFRPC organic sheets in the thermoforming process, will be highlighted. The nature of this staple fiber effect was investigated by conducting tensile tests under process temperature. Two different heating methodologies were chosen. First infrared heating panels were used in an open test rig in order to replicate thermoforming conditions. These results were then compared with tensile tests conducted by using a convection oven in a secured area. Finally, the results will be summarized and the impact of the staple fiber effect on the state of the art thermoforming process will be discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the year 2020, an amount of up to 20,000 tons of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPC) waste is predicted [1]. This is corresponding to an estimated amount of 12,500¹ tons of virgin carbon fibers (vCF) which is approximately 10 % of the current global annual production capacity [2]. These are eminent volumes of which 2/3 will be caused in-house (post-industrial) and 1/3 by end-of-life waste (post-consumer) [1]. Those figures demonstrate impressively that solutions on the question of how to recycle CFRPC must be found.

The state of the art of methods for CFRPC recycling (rCFRPC) shall be questioned. The established recycling processes are more a so-called down-cycling than a true recycling since the mechanical properties of the material cannot be maintained and decrease with each recycling step. Examples are recycled carbon fiber (rCF) non-wovens, rCF-compounds to be used in injection

¹ Estimation based on a fiber volume content of 50% and an average resin density of 1,2 g/cm³.

molding processes or even rCF powder as filler material in related applications. These processes are not suitable to maintain fiber lengths while also ensure defined fiber orientations.

2 MANUFACTURING OF SEMI FINISHED PRODUCTS

A true recycling can only be achieved by maintaining the fiber length and orientation in final parts. One possible solution is to produce continuous fiber reinforced semi-finished sheets, so called organic sheets, made of rCF/PA6 hybrid staple fiber yarns (rCF-SFY) as they are developed in the research project “InTeKS”. The yarn is being produced by a five step process. First of all the rCF, in this case residues from roving spools (Toray, Type T700GC, 24k), are cut into homogenous roving segments of 80 mm length. These segments are then pre-opened by a pin roll and blended with PA6 fibers. In the following the fiber blend is aligned by a carding process and formed to a sliver. In a final step the sliver is spun to a yarn by a spiral covering process in order to avoid fiber torsion. With this technique a PA6 filament is wound around the sliver, resulting in an adjustable compaction and thus forming of the yarn. Figure 1 shows the related process chain (excluding the cutting process in the beginning). This process shortens the rCF of about 70% due to the mechanical stress, resulting in an average rCF fiber length of about 25 mm in the yarns. [3]

Figure 1: Schematic process of yarn production.

Produced yarn counts are 400 tex and 800 tex. The latter is being used as warp, the first as weft in the following process step of non-crimp fabric (NCF) production (cf. fig. 2) [4]. These NCF serve as reinforcement structure for the final rCFRPC organic sheets and can be directly stacked without using additional polymer films. The usability of the NCF for the pressing process of organic sheets has already been successfully shown with a static press. The resulting mechanical properties such as Young’s modulus and tensile strength can be found in table 1. [3]

Figure 2: Detail of rCF/PA6 non-crimp fabric. From top to down in the background: 800 tex warp yarns (1). From left to right in the front: 400 tex weft yarns (2). White multifilament around yarns: PA6 spiral covering yarn (3). Transparent filaments: fixation of fabric with polyamide 66 monofilament (4).

3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

In order to investigate the mechanical performance of rCF-SFY, UD plates were produced by filament winding, followed by a consolidation in the autoclave. The specimen were cut out of the UD plates ($L/W/H = 250 \times 15 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^3$). Tensile tests were performed at room temperature in the style of DIN ISO 527-5 on a Zwick 1485 universal testing machine with a 250 kN measuring box.

For the industrial application of rCF-SFY it is essential to prove the feasibility of organic sheet production. Therefore, organic sheets were manufactured in a static pressing process. Four layers of rCF-SFY NCF were stacked (cf. fig. 3) with the warp yarns facing each other in order to use nesting effects, which leads to a better compaction behavior before the impregnation and consolidation is initialized. The laminate was pressed with 25 bars at 290 °C for 15 minutes. The resulting laminate of 1 mm thickness was cut into tensile bars in the style of DIN ISO 527-5 and similar to the UD bars tested on the same Zwick 1485 universal testing machine. The resulting tensile strength and Young's modulus are also given in table 1.

Figure 3: Stacking lay-out of 1 mm rCF-SFY organic sheet. (1): 400 tex weft, (2): 800 tex warp. On the right: organic sheet after consolidation, width = 340 mm, length = 480 mm.

Table 1 provides a comparison of the mechanical properties of rCF-SFY compared to selected materials. A virgin UD CFRPC [5], commercially available organic sheets from Bond Laminates [6, 7], and research results of Pickering et al. [8] are considered. Pickering provides mechanical properties of unidirectional oriented mats with 3 mm and 12 mm fiber lengths. The rCF Pickering uses are recovered by fluidized bed technology. All values are normalized to fiber volume contents (FVC) of 45% [8].

Considering that the type of CF plays a significant role for mechanical laminate properties, it shall be mentioned that Rapp uses CF of the type T300. In contrast the T700GC CF used in the rCF-SFY possesses a 25% higher tensile strength, but the same Young's modulus. Tensile strength and Young's modulus of used CF in the rCF-SFY have been determined in preliminary single fiber tests [10].

Already taken into account that T300 CF has lower initial tensile strength, the rCF-SFY reaches an 80% level in tensile strength and Young's modulus of vCF. Compared to the conducted research of Pickering et al., both recycling strategies, the yarn production and the aligned mat production lead to similar Young's moduli. However, the tensile strength of aligned rCF mats is significantly lower, which could be explained by shorter average fiber lengths and unknown fiber sizing conditions in case of the aligned mats.

The rCF-SFY organic sheets, which were produced in an industry-oriented pressing process, show attractive mechanical properties. Figure 4 displays the weight specific tensile strength and Young's modulus related to table 1. Even though the material is made of rCF, it possesses comparable tensile strength and Young's modulus to commercially available CFRPC organic sheets. Furthermore, it exceeds the values of GFRPC by 44% (tensile strength) respectively 152% (Young's modulus).

		rCF-SFY	rCF-SFY	Rapp	Bond L.	Bond L.	Pickering	Pickering
Fiber Type	-	rCF	rCF	CF	GF	CF	rCF	rCF
Orientation	-	0/90	UD	UD	0/90	0/90	UD	UD
Fiber length (avg.)	mm	25	25	∞	∞	∞	3	12
Tensile Strength	[MPa]	441	1065	1088	383	600	616	450
Young's Modulus	[GPa]	40,5	79,8	99,8	20,1	48,0	82,2	73,3

Table 1: Comparison of rCF-SFY with commercially available organic sheets from Bond Laminates and the research results of Pickering et al. [5, 6, 7, 8]

Figure 4: Materials compared regarding their weight specific mechanical properties [5, 6, 7, 8].

4 INVESTIGATION OF STAPLE FIBER EFFECT

The rCF-SFY and non-crimp fabric structure are intended to possess an excellent draping behavior when used in organic sheets. Due to the use of rCF with an average length of approximately 25 mm bound in the yarns, an inter-fiber-sliding of the single filaments shall allow a plastic deformation while being above the melting temperature of the used matrix (polyamide 6 with $T_m = 220$ °C).

In this section the plastic deformation behavior of the rCF-SFY will be highlighted and referring results from conducted tensile tests at process temperature will be shown.

To conduct the tensile tests, UD plates were produced by filament winding, followed by a consolidation in the autoclave. For this process a pressure of 24 bar for 25 min time at 265 °C were used, by a total processing time of 105 min. The specimen were cut out of the UD plates ($L/W/H = 250 \times 15 \times 1.5$ mm³) and marked in 10 mm intervals. Two types of material testing have been applied: tensile testing at melting temperature by heating with infrared (IR) radiation to prove the deformability during the thermoforming process and the heating with convectional heat transfer (oven) as a reference method in a secured surrounding. [9]

For the first testing method at melting temperature, a test rig was equipped with two infrared heating fields, pneumatic cylinders and clamps. Temperature was recorded with two calibrated infrared cameras, facing the upper and lower side of the specimen. Test specimens were heated up

until the specimen's center part reached 245 °C and then stretched with 50 mm/min. In order to gain a first impression on the stretching behavior of rCF-SFY, maximum elongation was limited to 25 mm in the first series and 15 mm in a second series. In a third series the bars were stretched until failure. The resulting forces were measured. Figure 5 shows the corresponding results. It can be observed that the forces rise until an elongation of 5 mm is reached. This can be explained by stretching of the slightly waved yarns which equals 8–12% elongation. After peak forces (static friction of fibers) are overcome, filaments start sliding and resulting forces decrease. Elongations of 40 % and more are attainable (40 mm elongation on 100 mm stretched length). To achieve a better understanding on elongation behavior, specimens were further investigated after testing by cutting them in pieces of 10 mm and weighing single parts. Figure 6 shows the related weight distribution. It can be observed that the elongation origins from the middle of the specimens which can be explained by higher temperatures in the center of the specimen. Specimen parts close to the clamping zones were less heated because of the radiation shadows and the passive cooling, both caused by the massive steel clamps (cf. fig. 5, picture). [8]

Figure 5: Force / displacement curves using IR heating. Tensile test is initiated by 245 °C specimen temperature. Picture: mounted specimen with solid steel clamps.

Figure 6: Weight distribution of two specimens after testing. In lower left corner: one segment of 10 mm after being cut off the specimen. Clamping zones (first three segments from each side) are not considered.

In contrast to the conducted IR heated tensile tests, which served for a basic understanding of the staple fiber effect, the goal of the convectional heated tensile tests was to investigate the influence of the specimen temperature on the necessary force to plastically deform the specimen.

The referring test rig consisted of two pneumatic cylinders with mounted steel clamps, surrounded by a convection oven. Temperatures were recorded at the lower end of the sample with a thermocouple in order to limit the constraint of the tensile test due to thermocouple fixation. Since the clamps passively cooled down the specimen at the nearby segments, preliminary heating tests were necessary to determine the temperature in the center of the specimen. This was achieved by mounting a specimen into the test rig, equipped with one thermocouple close to the clamping zone (cf. fig. 7, picture, pos. 1) and another one on the center part of the specimen (cf. fig. 7, pos. 2). A third control thermocouple was set in the oven chamber itself (cf. fig.7, pos. 3), measuring the surrounding temperature. The calibration revealed that the relation between temperatures within the clamping zone and the center zone are as shown in table 2.

Temperature clamping zone	°C	190	200	210
Temperature center zone	°C	210	215	220

Table 2: Relation of temperatures in clamping and center zones.

The tests were conducted by measuring the clamping zone temperatures and later converted to the referring center zone temperatures. The resulting curves are provided in figure 7. Each curve consists of three tensile tests. As expected, the resulting forces decrease with rising temperature since the matrix viscosity decreases as well, facilitating the inter-fiber-sliding. This also induces that, especially in the first 2 - 3 mm, lower energies are brought in the specimen. Once the static friction forces are overcome, the curves converge, but it can be observed that with lower matrix temperatures also lower forces are needed to stretch the specimen. This can be explained by a spring model: the preloads brought in during the first 2 - 3 mm are higher at lower matrix temperatures. The preload gets released after static friction (peak of curve) is overcome, which explains the second half of the graphs, showing lower stretching forces for lower matrix temperatures.

As demonstrated in figure 8, the inter-fiber-sliding occurs more homogeneously throughout the specimen length when the specimens are more homogeneously heated. While temperature differences with IR heating between the clamping and the center zone could amount up to 40 K, the maximum temperature difference for convection heating was 20 K.

Figure 7: Force / displacement curves using convectional heating. Tensile test is initiated at temperatures ranging from 210 °C to 220 °C. Picture: mounted specimen.

Figure 8: Weight distribution of two specimens after testing. Weights are given in mg per segment of 10 mm. Clamping zones (first three segments from each side) are not considered.

The investigation of the staple fiber effect showed that a plastic deformation of rCF-SFY laminate up to 40 % is feasible and the intensity of the use of this effect in later applications mainly depends on the acceptable material thinning due to the rule of constant volumes. In contrast to the conducted experiments with IR heating, the specimens which were heated up in the convection oven showed a significantly better stretching behavior. The specimens were thinned out at multiple spots. This is not supposed to be depending on the heating method but rather on the heat distribution in the specimen. Thus, in the later thermoforming process a homogeneous heating of the organic sheets should be assured.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The achieved results show that research in the field of recycled carbon staple fiber yarns can contribute to a real recycling of CFRPC. It has been shown that regained CF from spools can be processed into rCF-SFY in order to manufacture non-crimp fabrics. These are usable as semi-finished products for the production of organic sheets as it is shown in this proceeding.

The mechanical performance of such organic sheets is close to virgin CFRPC organic sheets, UD tensile bars made of rCF-SFY possess 80% of the tensile strength and Young's modulus of UD CFRPC tensile bars.

The plastic deformation of staple fiber structures offers new degrees of freedom for thermoforming of organic sheets and thus enlarges the field of application. Significant inter-fiber-sliding under process temperature is achievable. All in all, further investigations will be undertaken in order to generate a deeper understanding on the behavior of staple fiber yarns and their consequences to state of the art process technologies.

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